

A Comparative Analysis of Spatial Filtering and CEBRA Methodologies for Enhancing BCI Adaptability on ECoG Data

Dandawate, A.¹, Kharazi, A.M.², McPherson, L.³, Molina-Padilla, X.⁴, Srinivasan, J.⁵, Teyavongsak, J.⁶ Fahimi Hnazae, M.⁷

General Summary

BCIs assist motor-disabled individuals by decoding neural activity. Since these signals are highly localized, minor experimental changes can drastically alter model perception. Using ECoG data, we explored linear models like Spatial Filtering with Generalized Eigenvalue Decomposition (GED) and non-linear models like Consistent Embeddings of High-Dimensional Behavioral and Recordings (CEBRA) to better measure patient variability, separate distinct subjects, and cluster similar ones. While GED improved the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), it lacked class separability optimization. CEBRA captured a distinct latent space via a deep neural network but failed to classify stimuli on held-out subjects. Both methods alone were insufficient for robust classification, highlighting the need for hybrid approaches that integrate linear and non-linear models. Such combinations could enhance BCI adaptability and accuracy, ensuring more reliable neural decoding for assistive applications.